

GL MICAVE

D7.5 Public Communication Materials

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Executive summary

EUT is responsible for designing and implementing the GLOMICAVE communication strategy through its Research Communications Office, but all consortium partners are involved in it.

This deliverable explains and details the communication materials that have been prepared from M1-M18 including among others, the development of project's visual identity, the production of digital dissemination and promotional materials and project website, social media activity and press release written.

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List of abbreviations

<i>AI</i>	<i>Artificial Intelligence</i>
<i>EC</i>	<i>European Commission</i>
<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>EUT</i>	<i>Eurecat</i>
<i>VCI</i>	<i>Visual Corporate Identity</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>

1. Introduction

GLOMICAVE in a nutshell:

GLOMICAVE EU-funded project develops an **innovative digital cloud-based genotype to phenotype platform** relying on Big Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence (AI) and using large-scale publicly available and experimental omics datasets. This platform has the objective to assist experts and non-experts in identifying and understanding new links between genotype and phenotype.

The main ambition of the project is to **address the need to build systems to allow the use of primary data analytical processes and support large-scale omic experiments**, maximising the utility of omic data at a massive level and increasing the understanding of biological systems as a whole.

EUT is the partner leading the **Task 7.2 Communication Activities** (M1-M42), but all consortium partners are being involved in it. Task 7.2 aims to create and provide all the communication materials needed for conveying the project to a broad group of users.

All the actions will consider EC recommendations explained in the Participant Portal H2020 Online Manual section on project communication.

(https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm)

2. Communication materials

From M1-M18, EUT as the leader of Communication task has produced and designed **different types of communication materials and carried out communication activities**. All these actions have the objective to disseminate the project and catch the attention of both the scientific community and the industrial community, as well as the non-specialised audience about the potential benefits and impact of the research done in GLOMICAVE.

The communication materials developed during this period include the creation of GLOMICAVE's corporate visual identity, project's website and social media channels and the production of different promotional materials and a press release, among others.

Figure 1: GLOMICAVE Communication and Dissemination Channels

The following sections present and detail the main communication materials and tasks that have been done during the first two years of GLOMICAVE project by EUT with the collaboration of all the partners.

2.1 Project's corporate visual identity

According to the work plan, EUT developed GLOMICAVE's Visual Corporate Identity (VCI), aimed at **properly aligning all communication materials across all the project's tasks**.

The Visual Corporate Identity includes the project's logo, a Power Point template, Word templates for project activities and a visual identity standards' guidebook, which defines and outlines how to use the identifying elements pertaining to GLOMICAVE, including the different uses of the logo, corporate colours, fonts, stationery and graphic resources, among others.

Figure 2: Full colour logo (left) and Social Media logo (right)

Figure 3: Black and white GLOMICAVE logo

Figure 4: View of some pages of GLOMICAVE deliverable template

Figure 5: Stationery materials

2.2 Promotional materials

GLOMICAVE counts with a set of different promotional materials including an info-sheet, rollup, trifold, different business cases flyers, a project's general presentation, a poster layout and an animated video.

All materials follow the project corporate visual identity guidelines and are available to all the consortium in an electronic format, so they can be used every time a partner carries out a dissemination activity, such as attending to key conferences and fairs. All the materials are published on GLOMICAVE website (<https://glomicaue.eu/project-materials/>) and also, on the SharePoint repository folder.

Promotional materials will be regularly updated based on partners' dissemination needs and project's developments.

2.2.1 Trifold

A trifold describing GLOMICAVE project was elaborated during the first months and shared to all consortium.

This document contains an introduction to the project, the main objectives, key outputs, the platform to be developed, business cases, main results achieved and general information about omics sciences.

Figure 6: GLOMICAVE trifold

2.2.2 Info-sheet

An A-4 info-sheet, based on the main objectives of the project, the platform, the benefits and the expected outputs, was produced as a promotional material and published on the project's website.

Figure 7: GLOMICAVE info-sheet

2.2.3 Rollup

Two different version of a project rollup were produced to be used when attending dissemination events and/or to share through GLOMICAVE communication channels.

Figure 8: View of the two versions of GLOMICAVE rollup

2.2.4 Project general presentation

To support the communication of the GLOMICAVE project, a power point presentation was prepared. Each partner can add new slides and complete the presentation according to their needs and to the event to be attended and/or audience.

The general presentation designed provides a general overview about the project, its main objectives, the platform, the different business cases, expected impacts and general information about the omic sciences disciplines.

Figure 9: View of GLOMICAVE power point general presentation

2.2.5 Business cases flyers

Different flyers were produced with the objective to offer **more specific and technical information related the project's business cases**. These materials can be shared through more scientific and professional audience working on different areas related to these sectors.

For now, EUT designed **two flyers for each of these success cases**: blood markers predicting embryo transfer success in cattle fertility and fruit growth and quality management. These two materials were produced with the contribution of the partners leading each of the business case study.

During next months, more flyers with information of the other success cases will be planned at the request of the partners and based on the information they provide.

GLOMICAVE

Blood markers predicting embryo transfer success in cattle fertility

The project has received funding from the EU's Horizon 2020 programme. Grant N° 952908

www.glomicave.eu
@Glomicave_EU

Identification of blood markers to predict embryo transfer success in Holstein recipients

A precise and applied goal:
GLOMICAVE project aims at identifying different blood biomarkers in recipients to improve embryo transfer (ET) success.

A unique experimental set-up:
Data acquired on 400 embryo transfers performed on Holstein cows in France (200 ET) and in Spain (200 ET).

Timeline: 400 ET recipients (D0), Embryo transfer (D7), Blood analyses (D0, D7), Biomarkers identification, Pregnancy diagnosis (D40, D62), Calving.

1 Two blood samples performed on recipient females in your farm: at D0 (day of oestrus) and at D7 (day of embryo transfer)

2 Data collected on your farm, on recipients and their oestrus, on transferred embryo and transfer issues

Organisers: **Alice**, **SERIDA**

Figure 10: Flyer with information about the cattle fertility business case

GLOMICAVE

Fruit growth and quality management

The project has received funding from the EU's Horizon 2020 programme. Grant N° 952908

www.glomicave.eu
@Glomicave_EU

Identification of variables linked to fruit growth and plant phytosanitary quality

A concrete and specific objective:
Using GLOMICAVE platform, developmental and phytosanitary traits for ten fruit species at ten growth stages will be predicted and validated.

Fruit species: Apple, Clementine, Cucumber, Eggplant, Grape, Kiwi, Peach, Pepper, Strawberry, Tomato

Quantitative multi-omics datasets (allowing cross-species comparison), transcriptomics, proteomics and metabolomics and qualitative phenotypic traits will be analysed

1 The variables found, such as genes, proteins and metabolites showing relationships between genotypes and fruit phenotypes, could be used as targets to improve genomic selections and agricultural practices

2 In the case of viral infection by Sharka, the variables could be used as infection biomarkers, allowing the comparison between healthy and infected trees

Organisers: **AKINAO**, **INRAE**, **UNIVERSITÉ BORDEAUX**

Figure 11: Flyer with information about the fruit quality and growth business case

2.2.6 Poster layout

A poster layout was designed to be used and adapted by all partners when they need it. The document includes guidelines on how to structure the content and information along the poster.

The poster layout includes the following sections and content:

- Header:** GLOMICAVE logo and author information (Author names, Company name, full address, E-mail: info@glomicave.eu).
- Title:** Global omics data integration on animal, vegetal and environment sectors. Poster title: Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.
- Abstract:** Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Integer sit amet nulla laoreet. Donec et dolor aliquam, convallis vel sit, scelerisque malesuada. Phasellus non massa at dolor gravida, nec nulla non ultricies.
- Introduction:** Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Integer sit amet nulla laoreet. Donec et dolor aliquam, convallis vel sit, scelerisque malesuada. Phasellus non massa at dolor gravida, nec nulla non ultricies.
- Methods:** Title: methodology section. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Integer sit amet nulla laoreet. Donec et dolor aliquam, convallis vel sit, scelerisque malesuada. Phasellus non massa at dolor gravida, nec nulla non ultricies. Supplementum suscipit sit nisi. Ut velit nulla quam non condimentum vehicula. Nulla euismod ex leo. Maecenas mauris lacus, dignissim et libero in, varius malesuada. Curabitur sed nisi lacus. Aliquam vel nibh. Nulla euismod convallis. Phasellus non massa at dolor gravida, nec nulla non ultricies.
- Results:** Title: results section. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Integer sit amet nulla laoreet. Donec et dolor aliquam, convallis vel sit, scelerisque malesuada. Phasellus non massa at dolor gravida, nec nulla non ultricies. Supplementum suscipit sit nisi. Ut velit nulla quam non condimentum vehicula. Nulla euismod ex leo. Maecenas mauris lacus, dignissim et libero in, varius malesuada. Curabitur sed nisi lacus. Aliquam vel nibh. Nulla euismod convallis. Phasellus non massa at dolor gravida, nec nulla non ultricies.
- Conclusions:** Title: conclusions section. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Integer sit amet nulla laoreet. Donec et dolor aliquam, convallis vel sit, scelerisque malesuada. Phasellus non massa at dolor gravida, nec nulla non ultricies. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Integer sit amet nulla laoreet. Donec et dolor aliquam, convallis vel sit, scelerisque malesuada. Phasellus non massa at dolor gravida, nec nulla non ultricies.
- References:** Project partner logos and references. If needed please also reference collaborating entities.
- Footer:** Project partner logos (EURECA!, Alice, TRT, INRAE, ANICAR, etc.), European Union flag, and project website (www.glomicave.eu).

Figure 12: Poster layout

2.2.7 GLOMICAVE animated video

In what regards to audio-visual materials, a video was created describing the project's main objectives and expected impacts. The video, produced by EUT, has been shared through GLOMICAVE's Social Media accounts and has been published also in the project's website, as well as in the YouTube channel. See the video [here](#).

Figure 13: View of the video produced and shared on YouTube channel

2.3 Public Website

GLOMICAVE project website (www.glomicaue.eu) was launched in January 2021 (D7.1) by EUT, with the goal to serve as the main information channel for users interested in learning more about the project. The website displays the project's basic information, objectives, platform and expected results.

GLOMICAVE's website follows the corporate visual identity of the project and gives access to its social media channels. Additionally, the website is regularly updated with new information about GLOMICAVE, and conferences or exhibitions attended by the consortium. Deliverable D7.1 summarises and details the structure, the content and the functionalities of the website developed, as well as the data protection measures adopted within the site.

2.3.1 New pages created

From M1-M18, the GLOMICAVE's website has been updated with the publication of new sections to include specific information related project news, media impacts, project materials, deliverables, scientific production, etc.

2.4 Social Media

EUT is managing GLOMICAVE social media accounts, including a Twitter profile ([@Glomicaue_EU](https://twitter.com/Glomicaue_EU)), created at M1 (November 2020), a [LinkedIn profile](#), created at M16 (February 2022), and a [YouTube channel](#), created at M17 (March 2022).

Partners contribute to spreading the word through their corporate and personal Social Media channels, including accounts on Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook or Instagram.

The project coordinator is responsible for notify the European Commission about possible content of interest to be published through its official social media channels.

2.4.1 Twitter

The use of Twitter in GLOMICAVE project aims to serve as a channel to communicate about the project development to European institutions, academia and the industry, engage with members of identified stakeholder groups and promote the use of social media complicities between GLOMICAVE and other related projects such as FindingPheno, PHINDaccess, GenTORE and DeepHealth, among others.

Glomicave H2020 Project

@Glomicave_EU

Developing a multi-omics data analysis open platform to identify new links between genotype and phenotype. This account only reflects its author view.

glomicave.eu Joined November 2020

Figure 14: View of GLOMICAVE twitter profile

EUT is creating every month a content plan with different types of publications to be disseminated through GLOMICAVE Twitter account. In addition, all partners can propose new content to be distributed through this channel.

The different posts published include: content curation with information and news related to project's main topics, events in which partners have participated, dissemination of consortium meetings, distribution of promotional materials designed and the press releases produced, among others.

Glomicave H2020 Project @Glomicave_EU · Feb 4

The main results of #GLOMICAVE project have been summarised in a library of promotional materials that can be used for any communication activity or dissemination event

Download them here glomicave.eu/project-materials

Glomicave H2020 Project @Glomicave_EU · Jan 20

Partners from @SeridaAst participated in the International Embryo Technology Society Conference (@IETS_org) and presented two posters based on #GLOMICAVE research

glomicave.eu
SERIDA brings GLOMICAVE project to the International Embryo Techn...
GLOMICAVE project has been represented during the 48th International Embryo Technology Society Annual Conference (IETS) celebrated fro...

Glomicave H2020 Project @Glomicave_EU · Oct 28, 2021

The #GLOMICAVE platform tackles data integration, analysis and exploitation, with special attention to data governance, security, management and monitoring

Find out more glomicave.eu/platform/

Glomicave H2020 Project @Glomicave_EU · Oct 22, 2021

#GLOMICAVE partners have celebrated the first year of the project in Gijón, Asturias

It was great to finally meet you all in person! Thank you @SeridaAst @asincar and @ASEVAOFICIAL for the organisation of these two days!

glomicave.eu/glomicave-part...

Glomicave H2020 Project @Glomicave_EU · Jul 16, 2021

European #GLOMICAVE project to develop a digital platform to process large-scale #omics datasets using #BigData and #ArtificialIntelligence techniques with the objective to enhance our understanding of biological systems as a whole.

Find out more cutt.ly/ymK5n6H

ASINCAR and 9 others

Glomicave H2020 Project @Glomicave_EU · Feb 1, 2021

#GLOMICAVE website is live!

Spread the word about the project and its innovative multi-omics open #data platform to identify new links between #genotype and #phenotype

glomicave.eu

Eurecat and 9 others

Figure 15: Examples of tweets published on GLOMICAVE Twitter profile

2.4.2 LinkedIn

On the other hand, **LinkedIn** is a platform for the interaction among professionals to exchange experiences to improve their work placement. GLOMICAVE account on LinkedIn allows project partners to connect with the industrial and academic community, as well as connect and engage with omics sciences researchers and experts, Big Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence stakeholders.

The content publication in LinkedIn, which is less frequent than Twitter, is based on project news, events organised and participated, and reports and publications produced in the framework of the project or by trusted sources.

Figure 16: GLOMICAVE LinkedIn profile

GLOMICAVE H2020 Project
7 seguidores
1 semana

#GLOMICAVE #H2020 project is developing a new digital genotype to phenotype platform, relying on Big #Data Analytics and #ArtificialIntelligence and using large-scale publicly available and experimental omic datasets.

The project addresses the need to build systems that allow the use of primary data analytical processes and support large-scale #omic experiments, thus maximising the utility of omic data at a massive level and understanding of biological systems as a whole.

The consortium, coordinated by Eurecat - Centro Tecnológico de Catalunya, is formed by ALLICE, Treelogic, ASINCAR, AkiNaO, INRAE, Águas do Norte, S.A., NEC Laboratories Europe GmbH, Aalborg University, Universidade do Minho, Servicio Regional de Investigación y Desarrollo Agroalimentario, SERIDA, ASEAVA, Forschungszentrum Jülich, KU Leuven and UNE Asociación Española de Normalización

<https://glocimcave.eu/>

Home - GLOMICAVE

GLOMICAVE H2020 Project
7 seguidores
1 semana

Who is behind #GLOMICAVE project? A consortium of 15 partners from 6 European countries, experts in #omicsciences #BigData and #AI, that work together to develop a global omic data integration on animal, vegetal and environment sectors. The project's platform combines scientific knowledge from bibliographic public repositories and biological datasets to feed the #data integration platform for experimental multi-#omics

GLOMICAVE is a project coordinated by Eurecat - Centro Tecnológico de Catalunya and participated by ALLICE, ASINCAR, Servicio Regional de Investigación y Desarrollo Agroalimentario, SERIDA, Treelogic, AkiNaO, Águas do Norte, S.A., NEC Laboratories Europe GmbH, Aalborg University, Universidade do Minho, Forschungszentrum Jülich, KU Leuven, INRAE, UNE Asociación Española de Normalización

<https://lnkd.in/dBfSHA6Z>

GLOMICAVE PROJECT - Partners

glocimcave.eu • 1 min de lectura

GLOMICAVE H2020 Project
7 seguidores
1 día • Editado

#GLOMICAVE project applies Big #Data Analytics and #ArtificialIntelligence technologies to develop a holistic cloud-based platform consisting of three layers: data integration, data analysis and data exploitation, with special attention to data governance, security, management and monitoring.

The new platform developed will be validated in 6 business cases application, which will take place in three industries: animal, vegetal and environment.

GLOMICAVE PROJECT - Platform

glocimcave.eu • 1 min de lectura

GLOMICAVE H2020 Project
34 seguidores
2 semanas

Watch the #GLOMICAVE project video! The project aims to combine and analyse different types of omic data (genomics, metabolomics, epigenomics, transcriptomics, proteomics), to obtain relevant information and discover new links between animal and vegetable genotype and phenotype. To do so, the project is applying #BigData Analytics and #ArtificialIntelligence techniques to develop a multi-omics data analysis open platform consisting of multiple tools to maximise the use of omics data at a massive level and to support large-scale omic experiments.

<https://lnkd.in/dNbHwb5d>

Ver traducción

Figure 17: Examples of posts published on GLOMICAVE LinkedIn account

2.4.3 YouTube

The YouTube channel was created in M17 (March 2022) by EUT. GLOMICAVE YouTube account is being used as a video content repository and its content links will be shared on social media and through GLOMICAVE's website.

For the moment, the channel has **1 video published**. As mentioned in the *section 1.2.7 GLOMICAVE animated video*, this video gives a general overview about the GLOMICAVE project, its main objectives and expected benefits.

Figure 18: GLOMICAVE YouTube Channel profile